

Research Article

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Development of a Thin Layer Chromatography Method for the Estimation of Quinine and Ciprofloxacin

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ABSTRACT

A new, rapid, and specific thin layer chromatographic method was developed for the estimation of quinine and ciprofloxacin. Separation was achieved in chromatographic tank by using adsorbent material as silica gel which was applied on glass plate and mobile phase as acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water: (1:6:3 v/v/v) was found to resolve quinine and ciprofloxacin. Detection was achieved by using iodine flakes. The selected chromatographic conditions effectively separated quinine and ciprofloxacin with the distance travelled by quinine and ciprofloxacin 2.6 cm and 1.9 cm with the distance travelled by solvent 5 cm. This gives R_f value 0.52 and 0.38 for quinine and ciprofloxacin respectively. The developed method was completely novel, reproducible and specific.

Key-words: Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride, Quinine Sulphate, R_f Value, Thin Layer Chromatography, etc.

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INTRODUCTION:

Quinine sulphate is a white or almost white, needle like crystals or crystalline powder. It is slightly soluble in water, sparingly soluble in boiling water and in alcohol, completely soluble in acetonitrile. The pH of a 10g/l suspension in water is 5.7 to 6.6. Store in air tight containers, Protected from light.

Drug Profile:

Cinchonan-9-ol, 6'methoxy-(8 α , 9R)-sulphate (2:1) (salt), dihydrate

Chemical structure:

Fig.No.1. Structure of quinine sulphate

Molecular formula:

$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2) \cdot 2H_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$

Molecular weight:

782.96 g/mol [1]

Mechanism of action:

Quinine is cinchona alkaloid that acts as a blood schizonticidal and weak gametocyte against *plasmodium vivax* and *plasmodium malariae*. As an alkaloid it is accumulated in the blood vacuoles of *plasmodium* species. Quinine is less effective and more toxic as a blood schizonticidal agent than chloroquine. However still it is very effective and widely used in the treatment of acute cases of severe *P. falciparum*. It is especially useful in the areas where there is known to be a high level of resistance to chloroquine [2].

Drug interactions:

Acenocoumarol- Quinine, a moderate CYP2C9 inhibitor, may increase the serum concentration of acenocoumarol by decreasing its metabolism via CYP2C9.

Anisindione- Quinine may increase the anticoagulant effect of anisindione.

Artemether- Quinine may increase the adverse effects of artemether. Combination therapy is contraindicated unless there are no other treatment options.

Digitoxin- Quinine/quinidine increases the effect of digoxin.

Metocurine- The quinine derivative increases the effect of the muscle relaxant.

Terfenadine- Increased risk of cardiotoxicity and arrhythmias [3].

Uses:

Quinine is cinchona alkaloid that acts as a blood schizonticidal and weak gametocyte against *plasmodium vivax* and *plasmodium malariae*. As an alkaloid it is accumulated in the blood vacuoles of *plasmodium* species. Quinine is less effective and more toxic as a blood schizonticidal agent than chloroquine. However still it is very effective and widely used in the treatment of acute cases of severe *P. falciparum*. It is especially useful in the areas where there is known to be a high level of resistance to chloroquine [4].

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride is a pale yellow, slightly hygroscopic, crystalline powder. It is soluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, very slightly soluble in ethanol, practically insoluble in acetone, in ethyl acetate, and in methylene chloride. A solution has pH 3.5 to 4.5. Store in an air tight container, protected from light.

Drug Profile:

1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid hydrochloride monohydrate

Chemical structure:

Fig.No.2. Structure of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride

Molecular formula:

$C_{17}H_{18}FN_3O_3$, HCl.H₂O

Molecular weight:

385.8 g/mol [5]

Mechanism of action:

Ciprofloxacin has *in-vitro* activity against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin results from inhibition of the enzymes topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which are required for bacterial DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination [6].

Drug interactions:

Clozapine- Ciprofloxacin may increase clozapine serum levels.

Cyclosporine- Ciprofloxacin may increase the effect and toxicity of cyclosporine.

Lomitapide- The effect of coadministration of lomitapide with ciprofloxacin, and other moderate CYP3A4 inhibitors (such as aprepitant, amprenavir, atazanavir, ciprofloxacin, crizotinib, darunavir/ritonavir, diltiazem, erythromycin, fluconazole, fosamprenavir, imatinib, verapamil) is unknown. However, as coadministration is likely to increase serum concentrations of lomitapide, concomitant use is contraindicated.

Theophylline- Ciprofloxacin may increase the effect of theophylline [7].

Uses:

Ciprofloxacin has *in-vitro* activity against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin results from inhibition of the enzymes topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which are required for bacterial DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination [8-9].

Quinine and ciprofloxacin both drugs are used for the treatment of malaria and typhoid fever respectively. There are so many methods described for the quinine and ciprofloxacin but there is no method estimated for TLC for both the drugs individually.

Thin layer chromatography:

1. It is a chromatography technique used to separate non-volatile mixtures. Thin-layer chromatography is performed on a sheet of glass, plastic, or aluminium foil, which is coated with a thin layer of adsorbent material, usually silica gel, aluminium oxide, or cellulose. This layer of adsorbent is known as the stationary phase.
2. After the sample has been applied on the plate, a solvent or solvent mixture (known as the mobile phase) is drawn up the plate via capillary action. Because different analytes ascend the TLC plate at different rates, separation is achieved.
3. Thin-layer chromatography can be used to monitor the progress of a reaction, identify compounds present in a given mixture, and determine the purity of a substance. Specific examples of these applications include: analyzing ceramides and fatty acids, detection of pesticides or insecticides in food and water, analyzing the

dye composition of fibers in forensics, assaying the radiochemical purity of radiopharmaceuticals, or identification of medicinal plants and their constituents^[10].

R_f Value:

The distance travelled by a given component divided by the distance travelled by the solvent front. For a given system at a known temperature, it is a characteristic of the component and can be used to identify components.

$R_f \text{ Value} = \text{Distance travelled by component} / \text{Distance travelled by solvent}$

A number of enhancements can be made to the original method to automate the different steps, to increase the resolution achieved with TLC and to allow more accurate quantitative analysis. This method is referred to as HPTLC or "high-performance TLC"^[11].

METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents:

Acetonitrile (TLC grade), distilled water, methanol (TLC grade) was obtained from s d fine-chem. limited, worli Mumbai. Triethylamine (AR grade) was obtained from S. D. fine-chem. limited, worli Mumbai.

Table No.1: Working standards:

Drugs.	Supplier/Manufacturer.	Purity.
Quinine sulphate.	Vergopharma.	99.7%
Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride.	Clearsynth.	97.9%

Preparation of solutions for TLC:

Preparation of mobile phase:

The mobile phase was prepared using acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water: (1:6:3 v/v/v) was found to resolve quinine and ciprofloxacin. The chromatographic tank were stand for 20-30 min. And then ready for chromatographic conditions.

Preparation of TLC plates:

For thin layer chromatography the preparation were done by using silica gel-G as an adherent. Silica gel was taken in an appropriate amount in a beaker small amount of water is dissolved and mix it well. After the preparation it is applied on to the glass plates and distributed in same amount on overall three plates. Then it was dried for 20 to 30 min. And then TLC plates were ready for the experiment.

Preparation of sample:

For the preparation of sample quinine and ciprofloxacin were taken into small amount and added to the distilled water. Water is added to the drug so that it should completely solubilise the drug and small amount of drug particles to be remaining and taken into the capillary for application. Both the sample preparation should be done in different assembly.

Preparation of synthetic mixture:

Synthetic mixture preparation was done by taking one beaker containing quinine and another is ciprofloxacin. Both should mix together and applied as a synthetic mixture.

Sample application:

After the preparation of TLC plated and mobile phase the sample application was done. The glass capillary was used to apply the component on the TLC plates. To avoid the contamination of both the drugs different capillaries were used for different drug application.

TLC method development:

Selection of stationary phase:

Silica gel, aluminium oxide, or cellulose can be used as the adsorbent material for thin layer chromatography. But here silica gel is used as the stationary phase for method development.

Selection of mobile phase:

According to the literature survey mostly dichloromethane, methanol, ammonia, methylene chloride and acetonitrile were used as solvent for method development. But here for good resolution and separation purposes we used acetonitrile: methanol: triethylamine in water (0.1 %) used as chromatographic tank in the proportion of (1: 6: 3 v/v/v).

Application of sample:

Both the sample preparations of quinine and ciprofloxacin and one synthetic mixture were taken into the capillary and applied on three TLC plate. After the application three plates were put into chromatographic tank in bending positions and waits for the running of mobile phase so that it should run the mobile phase 3/4th of total length of glass plate.

Detection of spot:

After the application and running of mobile phase TLC plates were applied to dry on room temperature and put into the iodine flakes containing beaker. The observation shows separation of two different components as quinine and ciprofloxacin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Selection of stationary phase:

Silica gel-G was used as an adsorbent material.

Selection of mobile phase:

Different combinations of acetonitrile, methanol and water with 0.1% triethylamine were tested and the optimum condition at acetonitrile: methanol: triethylamine in distilled water 0.1 % (1:6:3 v/v/v) were selected. The optimised mobile phase shows the separation of both the drugs with R_f value 0.52 and 0.38 for quinine and ciprofloxacin respectively.

Separation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride:

The separation was carried out in chromatographic tank by using the mobile phase as acetonitrile: methanol: triethylamine in distilled water 0.1 % (1:6:3 v/v/v). Silica gel was used as adsorbent material on the glass plate. The detection was observed into the iodine flakes.

Fig.3. Spectra of quinine sulphate in distilled water

Fig.4. Spectra of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in distilled water.

Fig No.5. Mixture of quinine and ciprofloxacin.

Fig.No.6. Quinine sulphate.

Fig.No.7. Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride.

Table No.2. Separation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride:

Sr. No.	Drug	Distance travelled by drug (cm.)	Distance travelled by solvents (cm.)	R _f value obtained
1.	Quinine sulphate	2.6	5	0.52
2.	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	1.9	5	0.38

CONCLUSION:

The developed thin layer chromatographic method was novel, specific, reproducible, eco friendly, cost effective, fast and reproducible for simultaneous estimation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in bulk mixture. The method utilizes simple sample preparation, short analysis time. It is concluded that this method can be adopted by the industries and academic institutions for their combination drug estimation. It shows novelty and utility of the overall work.

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